

NEWSERA - Citizen Science as the
new paradigm for Science
Communication

Deliverable 8.2

POPD - Requirement No. 2

v1.4: Correction of v1.3

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 873125

DELIVERABLE DETAILS

Due date: June 30th, 2020

Actual submission date: July 31st, 2020

Project start date: January 1st, 2020

Duration: 36 months

Work Package concerned: WP8

Concerned work package leader: Science for Change

Dissemination level:

PU: Public (must be available on the website)

CO: Confidential, only for members of the consortium (including the Commission Services)

CI: Classified, as referred to in Commission Decision 2001/844/EC

Authors: Francisco Sanz, Maite Pelacho (Fundación Ibercivis), Rosa Arias, Oriol Agulló (Science for Change)

Revision history:

revision	date	Contributor	Description
v1.0	28.06.2020	Francisco Sanz, Maite Pelacho (Ibercivis)	First Draft
v1.1	30.06.2020	Oriol Agulló (Science for Change), Francisco Sanz, Maite Pelacho (Ibercivis)	Final Version
v1.2	17.07.2020	Nora Salas Seoane (Ibercivis)	Review
	31.07.2020	Rosa Arias (Science for Change)	Final revision
v1.3	25.06.2021	Francisco Sanz, Maite Pelacho (Ibercivis)	Correction
v1.3	29.06.2021	Joana Magalhães, Rosa Arias (Science for Change)	Final correction
v1.4	13.07.2021	Joana Magalhães, Rosa Arias (Science for Change)	Corrected Version

STATEMENT OF ORIGINALITY

This deliverable contains original unpublished work except where clearly indicated otherwise.

Acknowledgement of previously published material and of the work of others has been made through appropriate citation, quotation or both.

DISCLAIMER

This publication reflects the views only of the authors, and neither the European Commission nor the Research Executive Agency can be held responsible for any use that may be made of the information contained therein.

SUMMARY

Deliverable D8.2 corresponds to Requirement No. 2 on Protection of Personal Data (PODP). This requirement mainly implies that the contact details of the Data Protection Officer (DPO) are available to all data subjects involved in the research.

The partner responsible for the fulfilment of this requirement is Ibercivis Foundation and the Data Protection Officer (DPO) is Francisco Sanz, Executive Director of Ibercivis.

Ibercivis will ensure that each member of the consortium pro-actively discusses and considers all ethical aspects with respect to the activities that will be carried out in NEWSERA incubation, realisation, evaluation and all of its public engagement strands. The [ethical standards and guidelines of Horizon 2020](#) will be rigorously applied, regardless of the country in which the research or engagement activity is carried out.

TABLE OF CONTENTS

1. Acronyms	5
2. Introduction	6
3. Data collection and protection	6
3.1 CitSciComm Labs Data Protection	6
3.2 Personal data	6
3.3 Data sharing	7
3.4 Data collection, storage, protection, retention and destruction	8
4. Key Performance Indicators (KPIs)	9

1. Acronyms

Acronym	Description
CitSciComm	Citizen Science Communication
DMP	Data Management Plan
DPO	Data Protection Officer
GA	Grant Agreement
GDPR	General Data Protection Regulation
IBERCIVIS	Fundación IBERCIVIS/Ibercivis Foundation
KPI	Key Performance Indicators
POPD	Protection of Personal Data
SfC	Science for Change
UNIPD	Università degli Studi di Padova
WP	Work Package

Table 1: Acronyms used in deliverable D8.2 on Protection of Personal Data (POPD)

2. Introduction

Deliverable **D8.2** corresponds to **Requirement No. 2 on Protection of Personal Data (PODP)**. This requirement mainly implies that the contact details of Data Protection Officer (DPO) are available to all data subjects involved in the research.

The partner responsible for the fulfilment of this requirement is IBERCIVIS and the Data Protection Officer (DPO) - or Data Manager as it is named in the GA - is Mr. Francisco Sanz, Executive Director of IBERCIVIS.

The Data Manager has not found that any specific declaration on compliance and/or authorisation is required under national law for collection and processing personal data. Therefore, the designated DPO will ensure that all personal data collection and processing will be carried out according to EU and national legislations.

IBERCIVIS will ensure that each member of the consortium pro-actively discusses and considers all ethical aspects with respect to the activities that will be carried out in NEWSERA incubation, realisation, evaluation and all of its public engagement strands. The [ethical standards and guidelines of Horizon 2020](#) will be rigorously applied in the places where the research activities are carried out.

3. Data collection and protection

3.1 #CitSciComm Labs Data Protection

The Data Manager will coordinate that all signed informed consents are obtained and properly stored in each of the Labs, whether the activities are conducted online or in the local Labs briefly described in D8.1. The Data Manager will designate delegated people for these tasks within the NEWSERA consortium.

The Data Manager will inform the corresponding partners the distribution of the necessary information together with the collection of the informed and signed consents. In any case, the final responsible for each and every one of these actions to be carried out correctly will be partner Ibercivis, and Data Manager Mr. Francisco Sanz.

3.2 Personal data

In accordance with NEWSERA GA (p. 81), adequate measures to ensure personal data protection and confidentiality will be taken. [Regulation \(EU\) 2016/679](#) on the protection of natural persons with regard to the processing of personal data and on the free movement of such data, and the existing national implementations on personal data protection law.

General procedures to be included in the research protocol to safeguard the privacy of study subjects are as follows:

- Informed consent for the use of their personal data will be obtained from all the participants in the study.
- All materials obtained in the framework of the project (questionnaires, for example) will be identified through a code - the name and/or other personal data that could allow the identification of the participant will never be indicated. This unique identifier will link all basic data required for the study. The master key file linking the centre's study numbers with personal identifiers will be maintained in a password protected file with limited access.
- All files containing personal data will be stored in encrypted and password-locked files. Access to these files will be limited to authorized project personnel;
- Only researchers linked to the project will have access to personal data. Participants will know from informed consents who have access to the data, the name of the responsible and the personnel in relation to their positions.
- Reported study results will pertain to analyses of aggregate data. No individual's name will be associated with any published or unpublished report of this study.
- All project personnel will be trained in the importance of confidentiality of individual records and required to sign a confidentiality agreement.

In all EU countries, the General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR) - [Regulation \(EU\) 2016/679](#) on the protection of natural persons with regard to the processing of personal data and on the free movement of such data will apply.

More details are included in **Deliverable 7.1 on Data Management Plan**, by IBERCIVIS, in the framework of WP7 on Ethics and Data Protection strategies of the NEWSERA project.

3.3 Data sharing

In this section, data is **not** considered as **personal data**, but non personal information provided by participants through interviews as well as in a co-created way together within the consortium.

The results of this information will be licensed for non commercial purposes - once anonymized - under Attribution-NonCommercial 4.0 International (CC BY-NC 4.0), with no embargo to enable reuse. Exceptions may occur in some of the pilots in relation to specific requirements of the different stakeholders in the quadruple helix for each country. In those cases, other reuse licenses will be adopted to fulfill all requirements.

Nevertheless, alongside the process, participants can also decide in which way they want to share some of this non personal information. Maybe some of them want their research to be recognized nominally, as co-authors of the process and its results. This is also one of the relevant points regarding citizen science and communication and dissemination of results.

What the NEWSERA consortium can ensure is that no personal data will be shared without permission of the participants. IBERCIVIS follows strict security procedures when storing personal data, as explained in D7.1 Data Management Plan. In any case, the transfer of personal information will never occur to third parties.

3.4 Data collection, storage, protection, retention and destruction

As described in D7.1 Data Management Plan (DMP), there are diverse types of data, being many of them personal data.

Data will be stored by Ibercivis on their servers. Once in Ibercivis hosts, data will be mirrored to ensure its availability in case of hardware failure. Periodically, anonymized (meta)data will be uploaded to Zenodo, providing a DOI (Digital Object Identifier) for each dataset generated.

As it has been explained in section 3.1 on “Research participants” within Deliverable D8.1 H-Requirement No 1, the call for participating in the Labs is included in the survey managed by UNIPD. The privacy notice and information related to the survey and protection of data can be consulted there. Contact data of the UNIPD partner is available together with contact data of Ibercivis.

In any case, the responsible partner for Data Management is Ibercivis. The contact details of the **Data Protection Officer (DPO)** are available to all data subjects involved in the research, as it is indicated in the present deliverable **D8.2 POPD Requirement No.2.**

As an example - as it is included in **Deliverable 8.3 H - POPD Requirement No. 3** (see box) - contact details will be available in informed consent forms.

Contact details

If you have any questions relating to this consent form or the way we are planning to use your information please contact with Ibercivis Foundation, Campus Río Ebro, Edificio I+D, C/ Mariano Esquillor, s/n, 50018 Zaragoza, Spain. If you have any questions relating to data protection please contact the NEWSERA's Data Protection Officer, Francisco Sanz, tel: +34 876 55 53 96 email ethics@ibercivis.es

Data and personal data, when digitally collected, will use http over secure socket layer (https). The data obtained during the project, once anonymized, will also be uploaded to the free-of-charge Zenodo repository, when possible, by Science for Change. The handling of the local servers, as well as all data management issues related to the project, falls in the responsibility of the Data Manager from IBERCIVIS. The data is guaranteed for 10 years of unfunded effort by Ibercivis.

As previously stated, the handling of personal data will be done according to the GDPR, so participants can delete their personal data and unsubscribe from the project at any time.

4. Key Performance Indicators (KPIs)

Key Performance Indicators (KPI) will be defined to validate the impact and efficiency of decisions made. Examples of indicators related to POPD include:

- Number of registered participants, that is, quantity of personal data.
- Number of participants who request their personal data and download it.
- Number of participants who request to withdraw from the project.

These KPIs have also been included in the Deliverable D7.1 on DMP.